

EFFECT OF DOPO-BASED COMPOUND ON THE FLAMMABILITY AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF RAMIE/POLY(LACTIC ACID) COMPOSITES

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Keywords: 9,10-dihydro-9-oxa-10-phosphaphenanthrene-10-oxide (DOPO), ramie, poly(lactic acid), flammability, mechanical properties

ABSTRACT

Ramie as a kind of natural fibers reinforced poly(lactic acid)(PLA) composites have received a lot of research attention because of their excellent biodegradability. Poor flammability of the composites limited the application of the composites such automobile and aircraft interior area. 9,10-Dihydro-9-oxa-10-phosphaphenanthrene-10-oxide(DOPO) has been used to improve flame retardancy of PLA and its composites. However, the relatively large amount of addition of this kind of flame retardant would lead to the lowed mechanical properties.

In this study, DOPO with carboxyl group (DOPO-COOH) was synthesized firstly, and flame retardant ramie reinforced PLA composites were prepared loaded with DOPO-COOH by twin-screw extruder. DOPO-COOH in the composites are proved to be very effective to improve flame retardancy according UL94 test and limit oxygen index (LOI) measurement. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) shows that the improved flame retardancy was due to increasing char residue at high temperature. The effect of DOPO-COOH on the mechanical properties was also studied. The compatibility between PLA and fibers, which can be directly observed by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). It can concluded that the addition of DOPO-COOH enhanced both the flame retardancy and the mechanical properties of ramie/PLA composite. It will be helpful for the applications of the natural fiber reinforced composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the increasing pressure on the world's resources as well as concerns about the disposal of materials, biodegradable materials have received lots of research attention. Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) with high strength and modulus has been is a perfect eco-material for many studies during the past decade for its potential in renewable engineering materials. PLA provides good aesthetics and easy processability in most equipment. In processing and manufacturing, the price and inherent brittleness are the most limitation for its wide practical applications [1, 2]. Natural fibers were obtained from the leaves or the stems of the plants. As a naturally growing material, they possess low price, low density, high specific strength and modulus, no health risks, easy availability in some countries and environmental friendly [3]. By addition of fiber including sisal fiber, wood fiber, bamboo fiber, ramie fiber, and recycled newspaper etc. or other filler material including nano-calcium carbonate, nano-titanium dioxide, and multi-walled carbon nanotube etc., the mechanical properties, biodegradability, and thermal stability of the PLA based composites can be improved significantly and the price of PLA products can be reduced to some extent[4,5]. However, like other polyester resins, PLA and natural fiber have very poor resistances to fire because of their intrinsic chemical composition and molecular structures, so the modification of flame retardancy is indispensable.

In the past decade, several methods have been applied for the synthesis of flame-retardant biocomposites which include using halogen-free flame-retardants to obtain biocomposites with non-toxic and smoke-suppression properties, surface treatment, flame-retardant compatibilization, flame-retardant miniaturization or even nanotechnology to obtain biocomposites with good mechanical properties, and using flame-retardant synergism to improve the flame-retardant efficiency of biocomposites. Among them, low cost and high efficiency are the development directions for flame-retardant biocomposites [6]. Many halogen-free flame retardants containing phosphorus/nitrogen have been extensively studied and reviewed in the literature for their low toxicity and high efficiency. Most organophosphorus flame retardants form phosphoric acid at high temperature and prevent the burning of the substrate by a condensed phase mechanism. In our previous work, APP was added into ramie/PLA biocomposites, and the flammability of the composites were improved obviously. However, the blossom of transference phenomenon of APP can be found which could influence the flammability of the composites [7,8].

9,10-Dihydro-9-oxa-10-phosphaphenanthrene-10-oxide(DOPO) is a type of cyclic phosphate with a diphenyl structure(Shown in Figure 1), which has high thermal stability, good oxidation resistance, and good water resistance. DOPO shows excellent flame-retarding properties in the materials. Thereby DOPO can either act only in the gas phase by flame inhibition, or in the gas phase and in the condensed phase (by char formation) at the same time [9,10].

Figure 1: Structure of DOPO

In our previous study, DOPO was used to impart flame retardancy to ramie/PLA biocomposites. The composite can achieve UL 94 V-0 rating with the addition of DOPO. According to TGA results, DOPO can effectively increase char residue at high temperature, resulting the improvement of flame retardancy. It can be directly observed from SEM image that DOPO introduced into the composites disturbs the compatibility between PLA and ramie fibers. It can be concluded that DOPO can influence the mechanical properties of the composites[11].

In the present study, DOPO with carboxyl group (DOPO-COOH) was synthesized in order to obtain a new type of flame retardant. DOPO-COOH as flame retardancy was added into ramie/PLA composites, and the influence of DOPO-COOH on the flammability and the mechanical properties of the composites was studied.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) (NatureWorks® 4032D, having T_g of 52-58°C, T_m of 150°C and M_w of 140,000) was purchased by NatureWorks Co. Ltd.. Ramie yarn was supplied by Shanghai Qian-Cong Ramie Products Co. Ltd. (China). DOPO was obtained from Jiangyin Hanfeng Science & Technology Co., Ltd (China). Maleic acid, tetrahydrofuran (THF) and toluene were obtained from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. (Shanghai).

2.2 Synthesis of DOPO-COOH

DOPO and Maleic acid were placed in a four-necked round bottom flask equipped with a stirrer. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) and toluene as the solvent was heated to 90 °C and reacted at this temperature for 24h. After reaction, the remained DOPO-COOH was filtered and dried in vacuum at 50 °C overnight. The synthesis of DOPO-COOH was shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Synthesis of DOPO-COOH

2.3 Preparation of Flame Retardant Ramie/PLA Composites

Ramie yarn, PLA resin and DOPO-COOH were dried at 50 °C in vacuum for 10h, respectively. Then the dried PLA and DOPO-COOH were firstly well mixed. And then PLA, DOPO-COOH and ramie yarn were blended in a co-rotating twin-screw extruder (F:20mm, L/D:40, Jieya: Nanjing, China) at operating temperature from 155 to 175 °C. The extrudate was quenched in a water bath, cut into pellets and then dried in a vacuum oven at 50 °C for 8h. The composites are controlled by 10 wt% ramie, 10 wt% DOPO-COOH and 80 wt% PLA. Test specimens for the mechanical properties testing were obtained in the injection molding machine (Wuxi Haitian Machinery Co., Ltd., China) according to the standard. The specimens were prepared by the following processing conditions: barrel temperature 170 °C, mould temperature 30 °C, back pressure 4 MPa, and injection pressure 12 MPa. All specimens were conditioned at room temperature and 50% relative humidity for at least 2 weeks before testing.

2.4 Characterization

LOI values were measured with an LOI instrument (HC-3 Analytical Instrument Factory, China) according to Chinese Standard GB 2406-82 with test specimen bars (100 × 6.5 × 3 mm³). All of the specimens (125 × 13 × 3 mm³) were tested by vertical burn test instrument (WC 5400) (Kunshan Wancheng Analytical Instrument Co., China) according to ASTM D 3801 UL-94 standard. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed on a STA 449 C thermogravimetric analyzer (NETZSCH, Germany) at a heating rate of 20 °C/min. Samples were tested under flowing air (80 ml/min) over a temperature range from ambient to 600 °C. The morphologies of the impact fractured surfaces of the composites were observed and analyzed by scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Quanta 200 FEG, FEI Company) at room temperature. The samples were coated with gold using a vacuum sputter coater. The samples were viewed perpendicular to the fractured surface.

Specimens of the composites were tested for tensile strength according to GB 13022-91 standard using a CMT5105 Materials Testing Machine (Shenzhen Sansi Material Instruments Ltd., China). The composites were tested for flexural strength under three point bending in a DXLL-5000 machine (Shanghai Jiedeng Instruments Ltd., China) in accordance with GB 1449-83.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Synthesis of DOPO-COOH

FTIR results for DOPO and DOPO-COOH are presented in Fig. 3A. In the spectrum of DOPO, the absorption peak at 2385 cm⁻¹ assigns to P-H stretching vibration, the absorption peak at 956 and 1149 cm⁻¹ assigns to P-O-Ph vibration, the absorption peak at 1585 and 1450 cm⁻¹ assigns to P-Ph stretching vibration, and the absorption peak at 1209 cm⁻¹ assigns to P=O stretching vibration. The band at 3345 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the presence of hydroxyl groups introduced by atmospheric moisture. Comparing with the FTIR spectrum of DOPO, it is found that the absorption peak at 2385 cm⁻¹ for P-H stretching vibration disappeared from the spectrum of DOPO-COOH, and a new absorption peak at 2920 cm⁻¹ for C-H stretching vibration appeared, which indicate that DOPO-COOH was produced. Thermal properties of

DOPO and DOPO-COOH are determined by DSC, and the results are shown in Fig. 3B. The melting point (T_m) of DOPO is 119 °C, and the T_m of DOPO-COOH is higher than that of DOPO, which could reach 214 °C. The results of FTIR and DSC indicate that DOPO-COOH was successfully synthesized.

Figure 3: (A) FTIR spectra of DOPO and DOPO-COOH; (B) DSC thermograms of DOPO and DOPO-COOH

Thermal stability of DOPO and DOPO-COOH was compared with the aid of TGA analysis under N₂ atmosphere, and the results are shown in Figure 4 and Table 1. For DOPO, 3.5 wt% residues are left at 600 °C. However, DOPO-COOH remains 8.6% mass residue after thermal degradation at 600 °C.

Figure 4: TGA curves of DOPO and DOPO-COOH

Sample ID	T_{onset} (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	Residue(%)
DOPO	243.5	311.6	3.5
DOPO-COOH	359.9	473.9	8.6

Table 1: Thermal degradation temperature of DOPO and DOPO-COOH.

3.2 Combustion Performance

The flammability properties of ramie/PLA composites with DOPO and DOPO-COOH were evaluated by UL-94 test and LOI measurement. For ramie/PLA composite, the LOI value is 21.6%. And the LOI values increase to 28.3% for the composite with DOPO and to 29.1% for the composite

with DOPO-COOH, demonstrating that the flame retardancy increased with added DOPO-COOH. Generally, when the LOI value is greater than 26%, materials could be considered to have flame retardancy. The UL-94 results were also shown in Table 2. Ramie/PLA composite without DOPO is highly combustible and it did not classified in the UL-94 test. The flame retardancy of ramie/PLA composite is clearly improved with loading of DOPO and DOPO-COOH, and the self-extinguishing can be detected. DOPO was added to the composite, the UL-94 test results of the composites can achieve V-0 and serious melt dripping appeared during burning. Compared with DOPO, although flame retardancy of the composite was not improved with DOPO-COOH added, melt dripping was lightened. It can be observed from Figure 5.

Sample ID	LOI(%)	UL-94	Dripping
PLA/Ramie	21.6	NR	Yes
PLA/Ramie/DOPO	28.3	V-0	Yes
PLA/Ramie/DOPO-MA	29.1	V-0	Yes

Table 2 Flame retardancy of the composites

Figure 5: Specimens after UL94 Test

3.4 Mechanical Properties

Figure 6: Mechanical properties of the composites with DOPO and DOPO-COOH (A: Tensile strength; B: Flexural strength)

The composites with DOPO and DOPO-COOH were further evaluated by tensile and flexural testing. Data pertaining to the tensile strength and flexural strength are shown in Figure 6. It can be seen that the tensile strength of ramie/PLA composite was 35.1MPa. The tensile strength of the composites decreased, when the adding 10wt% DOPO. When DOPO-COOH are incorporated, the tensile strength of the composite is 34.8 MPa. Figure 6 also shows the flexural strength of the composites with DOPO and DOPO-COOH. The results were similar with tensile strength of the composites. The flexural strength and flexural modulus of the composites sharply decrease with the addition of DOPO. When adding DOPO to the composites, the flexural strength decreased. However, the flexural strength increased with DOPO-COOH added. This may be due to the fact that high loading of DOPO influences the bonding of PLA and ramie fibers. The compatibility between fibers and PLA becomes poor. It is well known that the mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced composites are greatly influenced by the interfacial bond strength. The compatibility between the polymer matrix and the ramie fibers is worsened by hindering interaction at the polymer/fillers interface. Based on these results, it is apparent that the addition of DOPO to the ramie fibers reinforced PLA composites decreases the mechanical properties of the composites. When adding DOPO-COOH, the compatibility between ramie and PLA was improved resulting in the mechanical properties of ramie/PLA composites increased.

3.5 Morphology Analysis

Figure 7 SEM photographs of fracture surface of the composites (a. ramie/PLA, b. ramie/PLA/DOPO, c. ramie/PLA/DOPO-COOH)

SEM micrographs of the impact fracture surfaces of the samples are represented in Figure 7. As shown in Figure 7(a), the ramie fibers disperse in the form of a separated fiber. The DOPO is well dispersed in the PLA/ramie composites in Figure 7b. No large agglomerates of the DOPO and good adhesion between the matrix and DOPO are observed, which should play an important role in improving the flame retardancy discussed above. DOPO adsorbed on the surface of ramie fibers or

blended in PLA matrix has an influence on the interface between and ramie fibers. From Figure 7a and b, it can be seen that there are obvious voids between the fibers and PLA. These phenomena indicate that the interfacial adhesion is weak between PLA and nature fibers. From Figure 7C, With DOPO-COOH added, the gaps existed at the fiber-matrix interface became no distinct, and the surface of fiber became coarse. These morphological findings support the results of tensile properties of the composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

DOPO-COOH was successfully synthesized and proved by the results from FTIR and DSC. DOPO-COOH could impart the ramie/PLA composites a certain level of flame retardancy, the composites could achieve UL 94 V-0 rating. Compared with DOPO, the addition of DOPO-COOH enhances both the flame retardancy and the mechanical strength of ramie/PLA composite. Morphological analysis shows the compatibility between ramie and PLA with adding DOPO-COOH. The new obtained carbon nanomaterial could have the potential applications in the natural fiber reinforced composites.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful for the financial supports by the Major State Basic Research Development Program of China (973 Program) (No. 2010CB631105), Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 51103108 and No.11172212) and the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities.

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